

Guidelines

On the use of BIM for energy performance

What information is exchanged,
when, why, and among who

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- the international group managed by Jeffrey W. Ouellette → Expert Panel: IDM Dev for BEM
- the BIM-EPA (Energy Performance Alliance), managed by Paul McCormack representing about 90 partners of several European projects dealing with BIM and energy performance.

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Executive Summary

This guideline contains food for thought to conceive a more sustainable building stock. The traditional building industry must leave the step to a more modern approach. The preliminary design cannot only look at the project as an end in itself, it must be conceived as one step in a continuous loop. This means that the author of the preliminary design must consider the consequences of his decision during all the life cycle of the building. To do better his work they must share the information and the decisions with all the actors of the supply chain of the construction industry.

This guideline should also help the owner, especially of public buildings, to understand that every coin spent in the deep knowledge of the existing conditions will be paid back in one or two orders of magnitude for the benefits received in the following phases, especially for the operation & maintenance which is usually very expensive above all for historical buildings.

Acronym and definitions

AIM	Asset Information Model
BCF	Building Collaboration Format
BEM	Building Energy Model
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
bSDD	buildingSMART Data Dictionary
COBie	Construction Operations Building Information Exchange
EC	European Commission
EPC	Energy Performance Contracting
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration
ESCO	Energy Service Company
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning

IDM	Information Delivery Manual
IFC	Industrial Foundation Classes
MEP	mechanical, electrical and plumbing
MVD	Model View Definition
PIM	Project Information Model
Roi	Return on Investment

Message from the authors

This guideline represents only one of the numerous possibilities to identify which information must be exchanged during the lifetime of a building to reach the best performance. In the case of a small building or even apartment, the processes can be simplified, and many exchanges will be in charge to fewer actors while, in the case of complex buildings, the roles identified in this guideline, can be still split among more actors. What we tried to underline was the importance to have reliable information to make informed decisions, and to manage the building for the rest of its life that, in some cases, will be forever.

We are open to contributions from any expert willing to share its knowledge to improve this guideline.

Introduction

According to the energy policy of the EU, each member state needed to identify and develop a series of energy-efficient goals and regulations, of which buildings are a key element, to reach the set goals. However, Europe has numerous listed and historic buildings, which need to become more energy-efficient and need permanent maintenance and refurbishment to fulfill the requirements of sustainability and use.

We believe that Building Information Modelling (BIM) can help to save costs and reduce the energy consumption of historic buildings if the use of open BIM is conceived from the beginning. Integrating BIM into national climate change and energy policies is necessary and challenging as many of these buildings lack reliable information, that BIM can help to generate, exchange, and, above all, archive, so that they can be used in the future independently from the software that has generated it. The use of open standards is therefore not an option but a must. In this guideline, besides the description of the exchange process in each phase, the list of open standards that could be used is also suggested.

The international context

The world is currently not on track to limit global warming to 1.5 degrees established during the Paris summit on climate change. The targets announced in Paris would result in warming well above 3 degrees by 2100 compared to pre-industrial levels.

If we continue as we are, temperatures will carry on rising, bringing even more catastrophic flooding, bush fires, extreme weather, and destruction of species.

We have made progress in recent months to bend the temperature curve closer to 2 degrees, but science shows that much more must be done to keep 1.5 degrees in reach.

The world needs to halve emissions over the next decade and reach net-zero carbon emissions by the middle of the century if we are to limit global temperature rises to 1.5 degrees¹.

The European member states are implementing directives related to the use of renewable energy sources and the energy performance of buildings. Meanwhile, European Commission has funded many projects addressed to promote zero or even positive energy buildings.

The result of this policy has brought to the realization of new buildings with very high performance but there is a strong necessity to improve the energy performance of the existing building blocks to decrease the high impact buildings have on CO₂ production and therefore to climate changes.

Among the numerous projects, EC has funded the European Calculator project www.european-calculator.eu that provides, among much other information, the current values and the foreseen values up to the year 2050, of heating energy and floor area and the final energy demand for space heating per building type.

In picture one of the possible diagrams to understand the trend and identify the roadmap that brings to reach the foreseen objectives within the year 2050.

On the 21st of July 2021 the European Commission, to reach these ambitious objectives, adopted a package of proposals to make the EU's climate, energy, land use, transport, and taxation policies fit for reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels. Achieving these emission reductions in the next decade is crucial to Europe becoming the world's first climate-neutral continent by 2050 and making the European Green Deal a reality. With these proposals, the Commission is presenting the legislative tools to deliver on the targets agreed in the European Climate Law and fundamentally transform the economy and society for a fair, green, and prosperous future. Among the different measures, one will guide member states to almost double the annual energy saving. The public sector will be required to renovate 3% of its buildings each year to drive the renovation wave, create jobs and bring down energy use and costs to the taxpayer².

¹ <https://ukcop26.org/cop26-goals/mitigation/>

² https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_21_3541

It is evident, therefore, that, especially in Europe, the market of building refurbishment will increase in the future, and we are sure that BIM can contribute to support the building renovation with more reliable tools to ensure the expected positive impact on energy needs.

Methodology used

The methodology used by the working group is based on the use of the BPMN standard to identify the exchange needs among different actors involved in the building renovation. In some diagrams ESCo (Energy Service Company), is introduced, as in Europe is in place a specific creative financial instrument, called Energy Performance Contracting (EPC), which can usually be provided by ESCOs.

EPC allows funding energy upgrades from cost reductions. Under an EPC arrangement, ESCo implements a project to deliver energy efficiency, or a renewable energy project, and uses the stream of income from the cost savings, or the renewable energy produced, to repay the costs of the project, including the costs of the investment. Essentially the ESCo will not have a profit unless the project delivers energy savings as expected.

The approach is based on the transfer of technical risks from the client to the ESCo based on performance guarantees given by the ESCo. In EPC, ESCo remuneration is based on demonstrated

performance; a measure of performance is the level of energy savings or energy service. EPC is a means to deliver infrastructure improvements to facilities that lack energy engineering skills, manpower or management time, capital funding, understanding of risk, or technology information. Cash-poor, yet creditworthy customers are therefore good potential clients for EPC.³

Figure 1 illustrates the concept.

In countries where ESCOs are not present the same roles will be played by the owner or an external consultant. The responsibility of the decisions related to the refurbishment works and the evaluation of the Return of Investment (RoI) is under the owner responsibility.

The exchange processes

The energy performance of an existing building is very challenging, above all, if the building is listed or belongs to the cultural heritage. In this case, the number of constraints can be very high, and the solution foreseen by the energy consultant could not be suitable.

At each stage of the refurbishment different information is exchanged among different actors. The stages we consider in this guideline are:

- Existing conditions modeling
- Preliminary design
- Developed design
- Technical design

³ <https://e3p.jrc.ec.europa.eu/articles/energy-performance-contracting>

- Construction
- Operation & maintenance and their costs

The actors involved in the exchange process and their roles

In the following paragraphs, the main actors of the renovation processes are considered. Some of them are taken from the document Information Delivery Manual (IDM) Development for Building Energy Modelling (BEM) (Version: 1.0 Date: 2021-01-29) produced by Jeffrey W. Ouellette and Paul Woodard. Other actors have been added to better represent the Italian/European refurbishment scenario.

Architect

The Architect is a licensed professional in the project design and delivery process. They are responsible for providing the architectural design of the intervention with formal geometries, spatial organization & functional programming, and usually also of the administrative procedures related to the intervention. They may also be responsible for providing material selection and properties, and construction systems that follow their design concept and owner requirements. The Architect is also responsible for the health, welfare, and safety of a design, ensuring that all due care is taken to provide a safe and secure environment for users. In the case of existing buildings, the architect is in charge of producing an "as-built" geometric model of the asset with the division into different "Uses zones". In the case of listed buildings, the architect is responsible for the intervention authorization process from the regulating authorities (i.e. Superintendence for architectural heritage and landscape).

Building Services Engineers or MEP Engineers

The Building Services Engineers, or 'MEP Engineers', are licensed professionals in the project design and delivery process. This includes Mechanical, or HVAC, Engineers for heating and cooling systems, of many variations in configurations, along with Electrical Engineers responsible for power distribution, communications, and lighting design, as well as Plumbing Engineers for water and waste-water systems, all working together in providing comfort to occupants and optimal design performance. All such engineering sub-specialties have an impact on building energy performance, as these systems are often highly integrated and can weigh their impact more heavily on a design, through dependent system type (e.g. heat pump/exchange, radiant, forced air, PV, daylighting, grey/recycled water, etc.) and fuel source (e.g. solar, geothermal, electrical, fuel cell, etc.). The design of these systems often involves a reiterative process, through a dialog with the Building Energy / Sustainable Design Consultant, to balance optimal performance with owner requirements and cost constraints.

General Contractor / Constructor / Construction Manager

The General Contractor (GC), aka Constructor, is the senior person or team responsible for the procurement of materials and construction of a building or facility.

They will typically oversee a variety of subcontractors and trades. In this context, they represent the individuals or groups who are responsible for the construction side of any design alterations during the procurement and construction processes. In some cases, the GC may be directed by a third-party Construction Manager (CM), contracted by the owner to direct and oversee the procurement and construction process. This may take the burden of some overall project administration and responsibilities from the GC, allowing them to focus more intently on construction and allow the CM to take higher-level actions and responsibilities when coordinating any changes with the other stakeholders.

Building Energy / Sustainable Design / BEM / Energy Management Experts

A Building Energy, or Sustainable Design, or BIM Energy modeler, or Energy Management Experts is a professional who specializes in developing an energy performance-based design approach within a building design process (providing performance best practices, energy efficiency knowledge, and dedicated design tools as building performance simulations).

They will provide input and feedback to decision-makers on design options, but in general, will not directly approve or reject designs. Commonly, these consultants will have access to tools, methods, and information specifically applied to a building type and location, or jurisdiction, for the appropriate simulation and analysis.

In this guideline will be referred as “BEM consultant”.

Building Product Manufacturers & Suppliers

The Building Product Manufacturers & Suppliers are companies or independent representatives who provide the various materials, components, and systems for the project which also affect the energy performance efficiency of a building. This may also include independent entities that provide BIMs of those materials, components, and systems, at the behest of product manufacturers and suppliers. The manufacturers and suppliers will be the trusted, definitive source for most, if not all, the performance characteristics of materials, components, and systems which the Architect, Building Services Engineers, and Building Energy Consultant will use in their BIM generation, simulations, and analyses. During the procurement and construction phases, they will also be directly interacting with the GC and/or CM.

ESCo

Energy Service Company - also known as ESCo - is a comprehensive energy service concept to execute energy efficiency projects in buildings or production facilities according to minimized project cycle cost. An energy service company or energy savings company (ESCo) is a commercial or non-profit business providing a wide range of energy-saving solutions such as designs and implementation of energy savings projects, energy conservation, energy infrastructure outsourcing, building retrofitting, power generation and energy supply, and risk management. The Building Energy / Sustainable Design / BEM / Energy Manager consultants could be part of their team.

Owner

The Owner is the ultimate decision-maker for the building. They provide and/or accept performance targets, budgets, and approve all design decisions based on input from the other contracted stakeholders.

For public work, the owner is generally referred to as **Contracting authority**. The owner is usually represented by the director of works, a professional figure responsible for the whole construction and decision-making process during the construction phase (see solely Responsible of the Procedure). Besides, the Building Energy / Sustainable Design / BEM / Energy Manager consultants could be recruited as a third part, to verify the proposal made by the General Contractor within the Energy Performance Contracting (EPC) with an ESCo. This person, in Europe, is defined as EPC facilitator.

Sole responsible for the procedure

The sole responsibility for the procedure, (in Italian “Responsabile Unico di Procedimento” -RUP) is foreseen by the Italian legislation in the case of public procurement. The RUP, according to law no. 241/90, carries out all the tasks relating to the planning, design, assignment, and execution

procedures envisaged by the Italian code, which is not specifically attributed to other bodies or subjects. The RUP supervises the development of the design, assignment, and execution phases of each intervention and creates the conditions so that the construction process is conducted in a unitary manner concerning the estimated times and costs, the quality required, the scheduled maintenance, health, and safety of workers and in compliance with any other legal provision on the subject.

Operator

The Operator has responsibility and decision-making authority for the daily operations of a building, and in general, is responsible for daily operational costs. The Operator will have insights into the suggested design alternatives to balance upfront costs with long-term operational costs including the materials and labor needed to maintain and replace installed components and systems. The Operator will usually have the responsibility to deploy and maintain any computer-assisted maintenance and monitoring & controls systems. His role is fundamental for the evaluation of the costs-benefits balance since the beginning of the refurbishment process.

Regulating Authority

The Regulating Authority, aka Authority Having Jurisdiction (AHJ), maybe a singular entity (e.g. a municipal Building Permitting Department) or involve multiple entities (e.g. additional Planning & Zoning Commission, Utility Services, Environmental Review Board, Superintendence for Architectural Heritage and Landscape, etc.). In jurisdictions where there is an energy performance component of building permitting and approval, the local regulating authority may have a role in information exchange. While they will not be conducting any modeling, in the pre-design and design stages, they may be providing up-front information on energy requirements and clarity on the energy codes requirements.

Before construction, the regulating authority will also provide approvals, which may be done based on the results of building energy model simulation and analysis. In some jurisdictions, regulating authorities (or quasi-regulating authorities) may also provide post-construction certification based on actual performance results in combination with the prior BEM simulations and analyses.

Existing conditions modeling process

During the pre-design phase, it is crucial to gather any information related to the existing conditions as well as all the documents related to regulating authority permissions, previous intervention, any change in use, the energy bills of the last three-five years, and all information useful to better evaluate the refurbishment strategy.

The plans and elevations of an architectural project, archived by regulatory authority offices, are, very often, different from the actual geometry of the building especially if the building is several decades or even centuries old. But, besides that, it is normal that an existing building has maintenance problems, and it is better to finalize the use of BIM for the operation & maintenance since the beginning to take all the advantages of the use of BIM in each of the following phases. That's why the survey of the actual building is always necessary to have a reliable digital model.

The economic implication fo this stage are very well comprehensible by looking at the phamous MacLeamy⁴ curve here reported.

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Patrick_MacLeamy

If decision are taken with the right information all the problems will be solved early in the process (green curve) with less cost and in less time (grey curve) and with less legal dispute (red part).

Actors involved

The actors involved in the existing condition modeling are:

- The **regulating authority** that provides access to the existing documents and authorizations
- The **owner team** has the following roles:
 - A **facility manager** collects any information related to the architectural status, the actual use of the building, the actual consumption of energy, the thermal properties of both opaque and transparent surfaces, the actual HVAC systems.
 - The **architect** verifies the actual geometry of the building by a geometric survey done, possibly, with advanced technology such as drones, laser scanners, photogrammetry, etc., and build the first digital Asset Information Model (AIM). At this stage the ownership and management of the Common Data Environment (CDE) must agreed within all the stakeholders to facilitate the exchange of information during the life of the building, and also to agree on design choices through the BIM Collaboration Format (BCF). The architect should use ISO standard 19650 that provides recommendations for a framework to manage information including exchanging, recording, versioning, and organizing for all actors. It applies to the whole life cycle of any built asset, including strategic planning, initial design, engineering, development, documentation and construction, day-to-day operation, maintenance, refurbishment, repair, and end-of-life.⁵
 - The **BEM consultant** acquires, checks and integrates the data on the building (geometric data, occupants schedules, HVAC systems, climatic data etc.) and performs the energy analysis in a dynamic regime. They identifies and proposes the possible interventions to improve the energy class of the building. The solution should consider all life cycle costs perspective and not only the comfort and its related energy consumption. For instance, the cost of maintenance should be considered too. Finally, the BEM consultant should know all national, regional, and local legislation providing both constraints and rules to access financial incentives. They must produce the certification of the energy class for the existing condition of a building because it is required to compare the initial class of energy with the class reached after the refurbishment intervention to access the financial incentives. In recent times it is also required to consider resilience to climate change.

⁵ ISO 19650-1:2018 Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) — Information management using building information modelling — Part 1: Concepts and principles

- **The MEP engineers** verifies all the aspects of the Mechanical, Electrical, and plumbing systems. They check diverse aspects of all the existing building services, by:
 - verifying the functionality of the existing systems;
 - checking the correct sizing of the systems in relation to the building needs;
 - examining the compliance of the existing systems with the normative;
 - aiding and supporting the BEM consultant for the proposed upgrading of the building energy performance. The latter point could include:
 - the proposition of diverse HVAC system layout and/or control logics;
 - the adoption of different technologies;
 - the adoption of Renewable Energy Systems; etc.

Usually, in this phase, which is only preparatory, the financial institutions and/or ESCo, are not yet involved. It is crucial that since the beginning the model is shared among all the actors to consider all the different points of view and make informed decisions.

The data exchange during this preliminary phase for energy demand calculation and simulation must rely on a sufficient data depth primarily regarding the definition of the building geometry and the thermal zones which both represent a container for thermally similar spaces and contain respective thermal and energy-relevant parameters such as user profiles. To be able to represent engineering systems, an exchange format must support objects to describe the building complete systems, individual components, the hierarchy of the components their functional and topological relationships, and interdependencies, as well as energy-related parameters or characteristics. For this purpose, XML-based standards have been used to describe geometric data, user profiles, weather information, as well as other energy-related data⁶.

The COBie standard is used to provide a uniform template in the form of a product data catalog that represents specific component data of building services elements.

This format is mainly used to identify manufacturer-specific systems technology and, thus, complements existing information in the ifc model.

When modeling the building, it is also important to model the network services, based on both traditional and renewable energy sources, to better define the cost of the refurbishment and the cost of energy during the use of the building.

The exchange processes

In the table, the abbreviation is used to identify the actors of this phase.

Responsible Party			
ARCH	Architect	MEP	MEP Engineer
BEM	Building Energy Modeler	OW	Owner
FM	Facility Manager	SE	Structural engineer

The exchange process, during the existing conditions, is represented in the following BPMN map and comprises:

- Gathering all existing documents related to:
 - Copy of the regulating authority permits
 - Copy of the building archived previous projects (plans, elevations, sections with annexed technical reports)

⁶ The BIM Manager: A Practical Guide for BIM Project Management. Mark Baldwin (June 2019)

- The existing building services components (collected on-site or from manufacturers datasheets), systems layout, and control logics
- Any service bill of the last three years (5 years would be better)
- Any other document describing any change that happened since its construction
- Gathering information regarding:
 - The actual use of the different zones
 - The temporal duration of use of the premises
 - The presence of renewable energy systems and their production
 - The systems (HVAC, working fluids production, etc.) control logics
 - The cost of energy withdrawn from the grid
 - The requirements for the desired energy performance
 - The requirements to benefit from fiscal and/or financial incentives
 - Yearly maintenance costs

All the collected information is exchanged with the architect. The first step will be the verification of the completeness and correctness of documentation to prepare the Asset Information Model (AIM). In case of incompleteness, they will need an update through the use of tools such as laser scanners, drones, photogrammetry, etc. to build a reliable model.

The AIM will contain:

- Necessary or required geometrical and alphanumeric information
- The link to the existing information regarding:
 - Substructure
 - Shell (both opaque and transparent surfaces)
 - Interiors
 - Existing services
 - Equipment
 - Building site work

Once the AIM is ready, it can be shared in a Common Data Environment (CDE) to exchange the information with the other actors of the process.

The BEM consultant, who could be the same architect, will be able, at this point, to integrate any lack of information, possibly with the support of an energy and environmental analysis expert (for example on the thermophysical characteristics of the building and/or on the HVAC system, on the hot and cold fluids production) and perform a preliminary feasibility study based on:

- Thermal comfort level required in each zone by the regulations
- Energy and environmental performance requirements for each zone
- Thermophysical analysis of the different elements of the building
- Environmental conditions, including shadows and/or borders with neighboring buildings
- Legislation requirements for the specific geographical area and the specific building (historical, listed, offices, school, hospital, etc.)
- The result of the analysis of the MEP engineers related to HVAC, domestic hot water, lightening, transport (elevators, escalators, etc.) presence of renewable energy systems. In some cases, it could be the same BEM consultant that performs such analysis.

It would be very important to establish, since this initial phase, the procedure for acquiring all the data. For instance, buildingSMART international provides a service called buildingSMART Data Dictionary (bSDD) that allows to build a data base of properties linked to analogous properties in different domains, in different languages and to ifc properties. It would be

therefore very useful for architects dealing with historical heritage, to use this service to create a “standardized” format to collect this information whenever dealing with such buildings. This means that whenever the same property needs to be used, a simple permanent link will recall those properties.

With the collected information, the BEM consultant can run a first “calibrated ante-operam simulation” and evaluate the current energy and environmental behavior of the building. Then they will propose some intervention to increase the energy performance and run a second “post-operam simulation”.

If the result is satisfactory the architect will verify whether the interventions are suitable (and compatible in case of a listed building) from the architectural or restoration point of view and will elaborate the Preliminary Asset Information Model (AIM), while the MEP engineer will verify if the solution is suitable from the technical point of view. All the observations will be reported, as comments, to the AIM using the BIM Collaboration Format (BCF).

The final consolidated AIM will be, later, integrated with the proposal of a monitoring and control systems for energy performance made by the MEP engineers. The following BPMN diagram represents the exchange of information for this phase. Some possible standards to be used during the exchange are “suggested”. The process can be viewed also at this [link](#).

The above BPMN is not the only possible process, and many variants could be conceivable. The key concept is that at the beginning of the process someone should provide reliable information that others would use for the next steps. This information should be guaranteed by whoever is providing it and stored in the CDE.

It is to be noted that the analysis phase, up to the calibrated ante-operam model, is the most time-consuming and costly operation. Moreover, the effort scales up depending on the complexity of the building. For instance, historical buildings require additional documentation on the historical and architectural analyses necessary to characterize the energy and environmental performance of the building. These costly operations are well paid back in the next phases that will be faster, cheaper and will provide better results with less uncertainties.

In the next table, the identification of the exchanges, the possible file format, and the persons that could oversee that specific exchange are listed.

Model Element Breakdown		file format	Resp Party	Notes
A	SUBSTRUCTURE			
	Existing foundations	ifc	SE	Only general information such as geometry and transmittance is required
	Existing basement	ifc	ARCH	It is important to evaluate the dispersion of the above rooms
B	SHELL			
	Superstructure			
	Floor transmittance	ifc/pdf	BEM	Sometimes is performed by the architect himself
	Roof transmittance	ifc/pdf	BEM	Sometimes is performed by the architect himself
	Exterior Enclosure			
	Exterior Walls	ifc	BEM	Sometimes is performed by the architect himself
	Exterior Windows	ifc	BEM	Sometimes is performed by the architect himself
	Exterior Doors	ifc	BEM	Sometimes is performed by the architect himself
	Roofing			
	Roof Coverings	ifc	BEM	Sometimes is performed by the architect himself
	Roof Openings	ifc	BEM	Sometimes is performed by the architect himself
C	INTERIORS			
	Interior Construction			
	Partitions	ifc	BEM	Are important for identifying the zones
	Interior Doors	ifc	BEM	Are important for identifying the zones
	Fittings	ifc	BEM	Are important if it affects the heat capacity of the room
	Stairs	ifc	BEM	Important to know if they need to be conditioned or not
	Interior Finishes			
	Wall Finishes	pdf/csv	BEM	Are important if they affect isolation
	Floor Finishes	pdf/csv	BEM	Are important if they affect isolation
	Ceiling Finishes	pdf/csv	BEM	Are important if they affect isolation
D	EXISTING SERVICES			
	Conveying Systems			
	Elevators & Lifts	pdf/csv	BEM	Useful for evaluating the consumption
	Escalators & Moving Walks	pdf/csv	BEM	Useful for evaluating the consumption
	Other Conveying Systems	pdf/csv	BEM	Useful for evaluating the consumption
	Plumbing			
	Plumbing Fixtures	pdf/csv	MEP	It is important to reconstruct the maps of the plants for maintenance interventions
	Domestic Water Distribution	pdf/csv	MEP	It is important to reconstruct the maps of the plants for maintenance interventions
	Sanitary Waste	pdf/csv	MEP	It is important to reconstruct the maps of the plants for maintenance interventions
	Rain Water Drainage	pdf/csv	MEP	It is important to reconstruct the maps of the plants for maintenance interventions
	Other Plumbing Systems	pdf/csv	MEP	It is important to reconstruct the maps of the plants for maintenance interventions
	HVAC			
	Energy Supply	pdf/csv	MEP	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Heat Generating Systems	pdf/csv	MEP	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Cooling Generating Systems	pdf/csv	MEP	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Distribution Systems	pdf/csv	MEP	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Terminal & Package Units	pdf/csv	MEP	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Monitoring Systems	pdf/csv	MEP	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Other HVAC Systems & Equipment	pdf/csv	MEP	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Fire Protection			
	Sprinklers	pdf/csv	MEP	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Standpipes	pdf/csv	MEP	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Fire Protection Specialties	pdf/csv	MEP	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Other Fire Protection Systems	pdf/csv	MEP	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Electrical			
	Electrical Service & Distribution	pdf/csv	BEM	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Lighting and Branch Wiring	pdf/csv	BEM	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Communications & Security	pdf/csv	BEM	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Other Electrical Systems	pdf/csv	BEM	With the support of the facility manager/owner
	Selective Bldg Demo			
	Building Elements Demolition	pdf/csv	ARCH	Recycling should be considered
	Hazardous Components Abatement	pdf/csv	ARCH	Presence of asbestos is a big issue
G	BUILDING SITEWORK			
	Site Civil/Mech Utilities			
	Water Supply & Distribution Systems	pdf/csv	BEM	important to know to identify which supply is in place
	Sanitary Sewer Systems	pdf/csv	BEM	important to know to identify which supply is in place
	Storm Sewer Systems	pdf/csv	BEM	important to know to identify which supply is in place
	Heating Distribution	pdf/csv	BEM	important to know to identify which supply is in place
	Cooling Distribution	pdf/csv	BEM	important to know to identify which supply is in place
	Fuel Distribution	pdf/csv	BEM	important to know to identify which supply is in place
	Other Civil/Mechanical Utilities	pdf/csv	BEM	important to know to identify which supply is in place
	Site Electrical Utilities			
	Electrical Distribution	pdf/csv	BEM	important to know to identify which supply is in place

The exchange for energy performance could be, indeed, more generic as far as concern the geometry, but as stated previously, it is very useful to have a BIM model that reflects the existing building as much as possible in terms of geometrical and information completeness to reuse it in the future in case of any future event.

The other consideration is that, in some countries, such as Italy, the structural engineer could oversee the structural integrity of the building due to the high risk of earthquakes.

Preliminary design process

If a high quality analysis of the existing condition was performed, the actors involved in the preliminary design will have all the tools at their disposal to perform the preliminary design faster and better. However, in this phase it is important to set up the “strategy” for the future uses of the model.

It is important, for instance, to decide at least that the model will be used for:

1. Schedule time and costs (BIM 4D and BIM 5D)
2. Managing the building
3. Organize and optimize the maintenance
4. Have a digital twin to keep the performance of the building under control

the different “uses of BIM” need to be agreed upon with the owner and be described in the BIM execution plan.

For the authors of this guideline, these uses are not optional but prescriptive if we want to achieve the goal of zero energy buildings by 2050.

Finally, a good preliminary design process provides reliable information for the assignment of a contract both in the public and private sectors.

All the actors of this phase will contribute to the improvement of the energy performance of the building during its lifecycle.

Actors involved

The actors involved in the preliminary design are:

- The **regulating authority**, in the case of digitalization of the whole permission process, would provide the rules to demonstrate compliance with the requirements. For instance, it is usually required to provide a report with the energy class of the building before and after the refurbishment work. The class is based on the evaluation of the active and passive properties of the building together with the identification of the different climatic zones with their different uses. In the future, the regulatory authority could use code checking software to verify that all the new parameters, foreseen in the refurbishment, bring to a higher energy class of the building without the necessity to read and approve a very long pdf report. For the time being, it will be very important if the regulating authority would make cadastral maps accessible and editable by the architect to view the impact of the refurbished building in the area where it is located as well as detecting any construction site problems.
- The **owner team**, with the following roles:
 - The owner/facility manager provides the requirements and evaluates the financial plan proposed by the ESCo.
 - The **architect** elaborates the preliminary design compliant to the owner’s requirements and develop the BIM Execution Plan (BEP). The BEP will start the Project Information Model (PIM) that will be used by the BEM and MEP engineers to

propose the technical solutions. Once the decisions are validated, they perform the clash detection to verify the absence of architectural constraints that could cause problems during the construction. In the BEP the architect will also identify the competencies necessary to perform the work giving each actor the role and the level of responsibility. If possible, they will provide a different level of information to the different actors depending on their information needs.

- The **BEM consultant** performs, working closely with the MEP engineer, the energy dynamic analysis based on the PIM provided by the architect.
- The **MEP engineers** propose, working closely with the BEM consultant, the upgrades to the mechanical systems (e.g. hot and cold fluids production system, HVAC systems, others depending on the building indeed use) and to electrical systems (e.g. power distribution, communications, and lighting design, etc.) based on the PIM. They could be supported by operators and/or producers, to obtain more information for the correct installation of the equipment.
- The ESCo verifies the economic feasibility of the refurbishment based on the PIM. In the case ESCo is not involved, the economic feasibility is performed by the technical office set up by the owner.

The exchange processes

In the table, the main actors involved during the preliminary design.

Responsible Party			
ARCH	Architect	MEP	MEP Engineer
BEM	Building Energy Modeler	OW	Owner
FM	Facility Manager	ESCo	ESCo

The exchange process, during the preliminary design, is represented in the following BPMN map. The process can be viewed also at this [link](#).

At this stage, it is important to organize the information related to the HVAC system, its auxiliary services, and its monitoring and control systems, (but in general of all the systems implying energy consumption) in a way that can be delivered to the owner/facility manager in a format that they can manage in the future. For this purpose, the COBie standard could be used. The following is an example of a table representing the information related to a fan coil. The example is taken by: The COBie Guide- a commentary to the NBIMS-US COBie standard⁷.

The following minimum set of information shall be provided in the Construction Documents stage design. However, it is important to define the minimum requirements from the preliminary stage. In this way, the architect can introduce preliminary values to be refined/validated in the next stages without providing the same set of information in a different format, each time.

For this purpose, a database of “BIM objects” has been inserted in the BPMN diagram. During this preliminary design stage, it is important to define the format and the Level of Information Need (LoIN) during each stage and use it consistently.

ISO 19650-1 introduces the term Level of Information Need or LOIN to define information services. LOIN is not a simple substitute for the LOD concept. The LOIN is intended for customers who define their information needs for project management. Within the LOIN concept, various metrics can be used to measure the information to be provided; in particular, geometry, alphanumeric data and documents for example, unstructured information such as floor plans, reports, photographs and so on. Alphanumeric information should be considered at least as important as geometry.

Construction deliverables will be updated to reflect installed equipment and other information described in the General Requirements Section.

⁷ https://www.bimpedia.eu/static/nodes/1010/COBie_Guide_-_Public_Release_3.pdf

During the preliminary design, the value for the majority of the fields of the table could be characterized as not available (n/a) and/or will report generic information taken from the BIM library of the software in use, in order to promote the export of the complete database through the open IFC format.

Heading	Typical Unit
Name	FanCoil-TypeXX-Space#-01
Type	FanCoil-TypeXX
SpecificationSection	(as identified in client's contract)
Location	(Space Name)
Current	Amps
Voltage	Volts
Frequency	Hz
Air Flow	L/s
Fan Speed	-
Exit Static Pressure	Pa
EnteringAirTempDB	C
EnteringAirTempWB	C
LeavingAirTempDB	C
LeavingAirTempWB	C
Total Capacity	kW
Sensible Capacity	kW
EnteringWater Temp	C
Leaving Water Temp	C
Chilled Water Flow	L/s
Cooling Coil Delta P	kPa
Cooling Rows	-
Fan Motor Power	kW
Phase	-
Cabinet Type	-
SpatialPlacement	(from approved list of placement types)
BasisOfDesign-Manufacturer	(If found on drawing schedules)
BasisOfDesign-ModelNumber	(If found on drawing schedules)
BasisOfDesign-Notes	(If found on drawing schedules)

The table with the exchange of information among the different actors will be the same as before, what's changed is the level of information and the completeness of the information. Having done this table during the existing condition analysis will speed up the preliminary design.

Developed design process

This stage is increasingly integrated with the technical design. The reason is that the AIM of the existing conditions has already been developed and the interventions on the shell and/or on the systems has been already defined in the preliminary design. Now they need to be sized to obtain the best performance with the best economic solution. The substantial difference between the developed and the technical design is the use of a generic BIM library at this stage and the development of the BIM library of the actual products that will be realized for the construction stage, in the technical design. However, it is important to refine the common data environment, the rules for the access to the information by the different actors, and to define the standards that will be used for the BIM library and the management of the building. The BIM collaborative format (BCF) will facilitate communication in such a way most of the problems will be solved at an early stage when any variation is still possible with little effort. Different solutions can be evaluated from the point of view of the architect, the BEM consultant, the ESCo, the owner, thanks to simulation software that provides the "virtual reality" of the applied solutions.

Actors involved

The actors involved in the developed design are the same as the preliminary design but with different roles:

- The **regulating authority** will need to evaluate the solution proposed by the owner team. In some cases, the evaluation goes through different offices, for instance, for a historical building situated in a national park with a high risk of earthquake, as it may happen in countries like Italy, the same design needs to have three different authorizations by three different offices. The use of a digital model stored in a unique place could facilitate and speed up the authorization process as the evaluation would be on the same digital model where each office could add his comments, requests for changes and/or requests for clarification. Besides, some constraints could be verified in automatic with software for code checking. A well-designed code checking can control any geometric parameter, as well as other, constrain like the presence of panic doors or architectural barriers. Code checking could verify the admissibility of the project according to pre-established criteria even before accepting the project, thus eliminating the waiting times for the admissibility check.
- The **owner team**, where:
 - The **owner/facility manager** will evaluate the financial plan related to the identified technical solution and will eventually request a more suitable alternative based on the Return on Investment (RoI).
 - The **architect** upgrades the AIM introducing the proposed refurbishment work. Once the BEM consultant and the MEP engineers have identified the solutions, the architect performs the clash detection to verify the absence of architectural constrain that could cause problems during the construction. They will manage the CDE and will organize the database of the BIM objects defined by the MEP engineer and the BEM consultant. They will also moderate the discussion using BCF and, on request, can provide the AIM with different levels of information needed by the MEP engineer and the BEM consultant.
The architect will identify the checking rules and use any software to verify the compliance to the requirements of the different authorization offices.
 - The **BEM consultant** updates the energy dynamic analysis based on the development of the design process and proposes tuned or alternative solutions if needed. The BEM consultant could be supported by an expert of lifecycle cost or life cycle assessment, especially if sustainability declaration is necessary as in the case of BREEAM and LEED certifications among others.
 - The **MEP engineers** propose the upgrading of the HVAC plants with “generic” products. For instance, they could write that a heat pump or a boiler of 3 kW will be installed, etc., this information is usually provided as a generic library connected with the authoring software. The mapping of the access to the services is also needed. It is important also to provide information about the maintenance cost that ESCo must use to better evaluate the RoI. They will provide this information with the support of operators and suppliers of the chosen technologies. They should know standards such as ISO 23386 dealing with the methodology to describe, author, and maintain properties in the interconnected data dictionary (buildingSMART Datadictionary, for instance) and ISO 23387 dealing with data templates for construction objects used in the life cycle of built assets. This aspect is important for asset management and the decommissioning phase. The use of the agreed standard is essential not only to avoid misinterpretation of the data but also to update them whenever a substitution is required or a change in the use of the building, and therefore the required energy performance, is necessary.
- The **ESCo** verifies the economic feasibility of the refurbishment proposed in the preliminary design to be described in the Energy Performance Contract (EPC). If for any reason the

solution is not any more financially acceptable, they propose alternatives. In the case ESCo is not involved, these roles are played by the technical office set up by the owner.

In the table, the actors of the information exchange.

Responsible Party			
ARCH	Architect	MEP	MEP Engineer
BEM	Building Energy Modeler	OW	Owner
FM	Facility Manager	ESCo	ESCo

The exchange processes

The exchange process, during the developed design, is represented in the following BPMN map. The process can be viewed also at this [link](#):

At this stage, the same table produced during the preliminary design and based on COBie will describe the generic products that will be installed/used.

The AIM will be updated and integrated with the database with the description of the products that will be used.

Technical design process

During the technical design phase all the final decisions are taken to ensure the best performance with the available products. The main role of the different actors will be the realization of the model of the building as it will be after the construction. All information related to the products foreseen in the construction, will be uploaded in the CDE, the model will be linked to each BIM object uploaded in the library. The connection between the geometric model and the BIM objects will remain connected so that any change in the product used, will be always registered and will be used to define the energy class of the building after refurbishment. The final document with the verified

energy class will be submitted to the regulating authority for final approval together with the technical design.

Actors involved

The actors involved in the technical design are the same as the developed design but with different roles:

- The **regulating authority** must evaluate the solution proposed by the owner team and will eventually comment and ask for integrations until everything complies with the requirements. In some cases, more than one approval needs to be obtained, as already reported in the developed design. Again, the use of a digital model stored in a unique place could facilitate and speed up the authorization process as the same digital model could be visualized by each office with the possibility to request changes and/or clarification before the final approval. Code checking could be used as a preliminary check, before the official submission, to speed up this process.
- The **owner team**, where:
 - The **owner/facility manager** will evaluate the financial plan related to the specific technical solutions and will ensure that the AIM is updated with the right information related to the products that will be used.
 - The **architect** upgrades the AIM and the database containing the information of the products to be installed. This information will be transferred to the constructor. They perform, again, the clash detection to verify the absence of architectural constrain that could cause problems during the construction. They perform a final check with code checking before the final submission to the regulating authority.
 - The **BEM consultant** updates the energy and environmental dynamic analysis based on the products suggested for the refurbishment.
 - The **MEP engineers** define the products that should be used during the construction together with the monitoring and control systems of the energy performance during its use. They will provide all information needed for the installation and maintenance of the plants. The information will be structured with the standard format agreed with the architect who manages the CDE and the related database of installed products.
 - The ESCo verifies the economic feasibility of the products identified by the owner team. In the case ESCo is not involved, the economic feasibility is performed by the technical office set up by the owner.

The exchange processes

In the table, the actors of the information exchange.

Responsible Party			
ARCH	Architect	MEP	MEP Engineer
BEM	Building Energy Modeler	OW	Owner
FM	Facility Manager	ESCo	ESCo

The exchange process, during the technical design, is represented in the following BPMN map. The process can be viewed also at this [link](#):

The table produced during the preliminary design and based on COBie will describe the specific products that the constructor should use.

The AIM will be updated, and each BIM object will be linked to the elements of the COBie table.

Construction process

In the traditional construction process, the loss of information reaches its highest level. The constructor has not been involved in the previous phases and they usually receive some drawings which they interpret following his own experience. In a BIM process, the constructor has to both perform the refurbishment, as it has been conceived by the owner team and/or by the ESCo, and to transfer the information of what done to the owner, to update the BIM model. The integrated model, when interfaced with the monitoring system, will constitute the digital twin of the building ready for any future use.

It is important, therefore, that the owner team provides CDE access to the constructor and is ready to provide any explanation related to the decision taken. The constructor has to be an expert in BIM and will use the model to provide the schedule and the distribution of the costs over time (BIM 4D and BIM 5D).

He will use the model also to define the layout of the building site and verify, in advance, the accessibility to the building with the equipment necessary to perform the refurbishment work.

Also, the operators have a very important role as they must read the model and update the information related to any other successive information such as the warranties duration, the instruction for maintenance and disposal, and any accessibility requirements to the plants.

Actors involved

The actors involved during the construction have the following roles:

- The **regulating authority** has a passive role, during the construction. It will register the start of the work and will organize controls on the building site. When the work will be finished,

they will receive the final model to be stored. In the case of unexpected variation on what was planned, they could ask to start again the authorization process. It will also store the energy class associated with the building.

- The **owner team**, will perform the following roles:
 - The **technical office**, which could be the owner itself, sign the contract and approves any variation related to substitutions, and ensures that the AIM is updated.
 - The **architect** provides the constructor with the AIM and the COBie files, containing the information of the products to be installed. They could be commissioned by the owner to supervise the refurbishment work. In any case they will update the AIM if any variation occurs. In the case the products, foreseen in the technical design, are not available or are not suitable for any reason, they monitor the substitutions phase and modify the AIM. They perform the clash analysis to evaluate any clearance conflict during the installations. They also have to monitor the choice of materials and products with the least environmental impact, eventually with the support of a life cycle expert.
 - The **MEP engineer** supervises the systems and equipment installations and ensures that the monitoring system is installed correctly. To have complete control of the building performance, the MEP engineer should design the monitoring system with several sensors that control both human and machine behaviors. They also update the AIM with the final layout of all the plants and they are in charge of technical testing of the installed plants.
- The **constructor** will receive the technical design and must take care of the supply of the products not only from the physical point of view but also from the data acquisition. The schedule of the work and the use of financial resources should be prepared based on the model received by the architect. This means to produce the 4D and 5D models. If any change occurs in the supply, they must inform the owner and/or the ESCo to ensure that the financial plan is maintained. They must pass the new information related to the substitution, to the architect to update the AIM. At the end of the refurbishment work, they must ensure that all the information related to the installed product is accessible, in the right format, and delivered to the owner/facility manager for the operation & management. Finally, the monitoring system should be tested by the MEP engineer to guarantee that all the parameters, for the foreseen energy performance, are maintained.
In complex buildings, laser scanners and/or drones could support the constructor and/or the architect, in monitoring the work to ensure that everything is realized as it was foreseen in the technical design. The collaborative platform can be used to share information with suppliers. This could be very useful if prefabricated products are used as the supplier can verify the sizing without being on the building site.
- The **operator** is the person that materially will install equipment and will intervene in the building site. They must know how to read a BIM model and all the information necessary to operate in a workmanlike manner. If any change occurs to what has been foreseen in the technical design, they must inform the constructor and/or the MEP engineer who will be in charge to update the model.
- The **ESCo** needs to verify that the financial plan is maintained as approved, and eventually modify it if any change to the technical design occurs. In the case ESCo is not involved, this role is performed by the owner team.

The exchange processes

In the table, the actors of the information exchange.

Responsible Party			
ARCH	Architect	MEP	MEP Engineer
CO	Constructor	OW	Owner
FM	Facility Manager	ESCO	ESCO
OP	Operator		

The exchange process, during the construction, is represented in the following BPMN map. The process can be viewed also at this [link](#):

The table produced during the preliminary design and based on COBie or other international standards will be populated with all the technical schemes of the installed products together with information for their control, maintenance, and decommissioning. This means that the AIM will be updated, and each BIM object will be linked to the elements of the COBie table and to the monitoring system to obtain the “twin model”. This model can be used to keep under control all the systems by the owner or his delegate (facility manager, ESCo, external service, etc.). In addition, the Beneficial Occupancy and As-Built Deliverables shall provide the following additional attributes:

- ElectricalPanelName
- ElectricalPanelCircuit

Operation & maintenance process

The operation & maintenance is the process where all the mistakes of the previous phases could bring to double the energy consumption or even more. The monitoring of the energy performance is essential to keep under control the foreseen values. It is also important to understand if any increase in consumption is due to the misbehaviour of the inhabitants or to the bad functioning of the systems. This is the reason why the MEP engineer must design the monitoring system with several sensors that control both human and machine behaviors.

Correct monitoring and management are essential to:

- Decrease the use of natural sources
- Decrease the cost of use of the facilities
- Ensure the right comfort for the health of inhabitants
- Intervene on the equipment as soon as malfunctioning occurs

Actors involved

The actors involved during the operation & maintenance are:

- The **owner team**, where:
 - The **Facility manager**, who could be the owner itself, will use the twin model to monitor and control the performance of the building and will organize the maintenance in:
 - Predictive maintenance that helps to predict the likelihood of future failures that could impact the building's performance.
 - Scheduled maintenance, for instance, the change and/or cleaning of filters, valves, etc.
 - Extraordinary maintenance, whenever there is a failure not foreseen in the predictive or scheduled maintenance.

They will manage all the maintenance requests both with internal resources and external services. They will also keep records of all the warranties to be used for maintenance.

In the presence of a contract with an ESCo, this role is under ESCo's responsibility but only for the lifetime of the signed contract.

The owner must avoid loss of data by signing a contract with a service provider or storing the data on his system with a valid backup system, or with a contract signed with the model author.

- The **architect**, or **MEP engineer**, or the **facility manager** will update the AIM and the COBie file linked to it at each maintenance intervention. Erroneous data could cause unpredictable problems. The AIM will be represented with an ifc file linked to external sources describing the elements that need maintenance.
- The **Operator** will perform the maintenance, will provide information to update the AIM and provide all the necessary information for any future intervention on the property.
- The **supplier** is an external entity that would be in charge of any necessity, and especially for the extraordinary maintenance. They will provide the information necessary to update the AIM.
- The **ESCo** verifies that the financial plan is maintained as approved, and eventually modifies it if any change to the technical design occurs. They will take care of the maintenance, as described above. It is important to underline that ESCo is obliged to take care of the maintenance for all the duration of the EPC. Besides, if any substantial change in climate and/or use of building occurs, they will adjust the HVAC systems and any other system using natural sources, to decrease the environmental impact. In the case ESCo is not involved, all these roles are performed by the owner team.

The exchange processes

In the table, the actors of the information exchange.

Responsible Party			
ARCH	Architect	MEP	MEP Engineer
OP	Operator	OW	Owner
FM	Facility Manager	ESCo	ESCo
SU	Supplier		

The exchange process, during the Operation & Maintenance, is represented in the following BPMN map. The process can be viewed also at this [link](#):

The operation & maintenance will be very efficient and effective if at the end of the construction phase, the owner will receive the AIM and will keep it for any future need. They must also receive the COBie file populated with all the technical schemes of the installed products together with information for their control and maintenance. In the case the digital twin is realized, the owner/facility manager could use the model to optimize the plants and/or decide which system be on or off and when, just using the virtual model of the installed products.

Which standards should be used during the exchange processes?

In the above BPMN diagrams, some standards to exchange information are suggested. What is important to underline is that the standards, when agreed since the beginning with the different actors, will:

- Facilitate communication among the different actors
- Ensure the consistency of the data through the whole lifecycle of the building
- Ensure the readability of the data in the future by anyone that needs it
- Allow the implementation of the digital twin of the building for remote control & management
- Simplify and reduce the costs of operational & management

When BIM will be fully integrated into all processes including the authorization process, other advantages will be:

- Speed up the authorization process
- Facilitate the certification, through blockchain, of the authenticity of any permit and any contract in the digital format
- Have centralized storage of the building design for other uses, such as the identification of energy district to be realized, or the optimization of the public transport, etc.
- Accessible strategic data to make decisions or intervene in the case of natural disasters as well as an accident caused by humans
- Design with closed cycle principles, that is to be able to reuse or recycle all the products used in the construction and/or refurbishment of the building

In this guideline, some standards are suggested but other solutions are suitable as long they are open standards and are used by all the actors.

Here is provided a list of the standards already published or under development and other general information that could be useful when using this guideline.

- **ISO 19650-1:2018** → Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modeling (BIM) — Information management using building information modeling — Part 1: Concepts and principles. This document outlines the concepts and principles for information management at a stage of maturity described as "building information modeling (BIM) according to the ISO 19650 series". This standard provides recommendations for a framework to manage information including exchanging, recording, versioning, and organizing for all actors. This document applies to the whole life cycle of any built asset, including strategic planning, initial design, engineering, development, documentation and construction, day-to-day operation, maintenance, refurbishment, repair, and end-of-life. It can also be adapted to assets or projects of any scale and complexity, so as not to hamper the flexibility and versatility that characterize the large range of potential procurement strategies and to address the cost of implementing this document.⁸
- **ISO 19650-3:2020** → The document specifies requirements for information management, in the form of a management process, within the context of the operational phase of assets and the exchanges of information within it, using building information modelling. The document can be applied to all types of assets and by organizations of all types and sizes involved in the operational phase of assets. The requirements in the document can be achieved through direct actions carried out by the organization in question or can be delegated to another party.⁹
- **ISO 16739-1:2018** → ISO 16739-1:2018 Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) for data sharing in the construction and facility management industries — Part 1: Data schema
The Industry Foundation Classes, IFC, are an open international standard for Building Information Model (BIM) data that are exchanged and shared among software applications used by the various participants in the construction or facility management industry sector. The standard includes definitions that cover data required for buildings over their life cycle.

⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/68078.html>

⁹ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:19650:-3:ed-1:v1:en>

This release, and upcoming releases, extend the scope to include data definitions for infrastructure assets over their life cycle as well.

The Industry Foundation Classes specify a data schema and an exchange file format structure. The data schema is defined in:

- EXPRESS data specification language, defined in ISO 10303-11,
- XML Schema definition language (XSD), defined in XML Schema W3C Recommendation, whereas the EXPRESS schema definition is the source and the XML schema definition is generated from the EXPRESS schema according to the mapping rules defined in ISO 10303-28. The exchange file formats for exchanging and sharing data according to the conceptual schema are:

- Clear text encoding of the exchange structure, defined in ISO 10303-21,
- Extensible Markup Language (XML), defined in XML W3C Recommendation.

Alternative exchange file formats may be used if they conform to the data schemas.

ISO 16739-1:2017 of IFC consists of the data schemas, represented as an EXPRESS schema and an XML schema, and reference data, represented as definitions of property and quantity names, and formal and informative descriptions.

A subset of the data schema and referenced data is referred to as a Model View Definition (MVD). A particular MVD is defined to support one or many recognized workflows in the construction and facility management industry sector. Each workflow identifies data exchange requirements for software applications. Conforming software applications need to identify the model view definition they conform to. Ifc is a standardized, digital description of the built asset industry. It is an open, international standard () and promotes vendor-neutral, or agnostic, and usable capabilities across a wide range of hardware devices, software platforms, and interfaces for many different use cases¹⁰.

- **ISO 29481-1:2016** Building information models — Information delivery manual — Part 1: Methodology and format

ISO 29481-1:2016 specifies:

- a methodology that links the business processes undertaken during the construction of built facilities with the specification of information that is required by these processes, and
- a way to map and describe the information processes across the life cycle of construction works.

ISO 29481-1:2016 is intended to facilitate interoperability between software applications used during all stages of the life cycle of construction works, including briefing, design, documentation, construction, operation and maintenance, and demolition. It promotes digital collaboration between actors in the construction process and provides a basis for accurate, reliable, repeatable, and high-quality information exchange.¹¹

- **Pdf** → PDF is a standard (ISO 19005) for encoding documents in an "as printed" form that is portable between systems. However, the suitability of a PDF file for archival preservation depends on options chosen when the PDF is created: most notably, whether to embed the necessary fonts for rendering the document; whether to use encryption; and whether to preserve additional information from the original document beyond what is needed to print it.¹²

¹⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/70303.html>

¹¹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/60553.html>

¹² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/PDF/A>

- **BCF** → In general, the BIM Collaboration Format (BCF) allows different BIM applications to communicate model-based issues with each other by leveraging IFC models that have been previously shared among project collaborators. This can be done by utilizing a file exchange between software platforms or using a RESTful service that connects software platforms directly or to a dedicated 3rd-party BCF server acting as the hub for such communications. More specifically, BCF works by transferring XML formatted data, which is contextualized information about an issue or problem directly referencing a view, captured via PNG and IFC coordinates, and elements of a BIM, as referenced via their IFC GUIDs, from one application to another. Several use cases can benefit from BCF-enabled workflows, where information can be derived from the BIM and connected back to the BIM for object-specific information. These cases may include:
 - Design phase:
 - Documenting quality assurance/quality checking (QA/QC) items of BIMs
 - Identifying design coordination (aka clash detection) issues between domain BIMs
 - Annotating design options, object substitutions, and material selections
 - Procurement phase:
 - Bidding coordination items and clarifications
 - Cost and supplier information for objects, assemblies, and/or systems
 - Construction phase:
 - Quality assurance/quality checking (QA/QC) records of installations vs. BIMs
 - The tracking availability of items/materials and coordinating substitutions
 - Collection of last-minute information for handover to owner/operator as part of the COBie deliverables
 - Operations phase:
 - Notations to handover models as changes are made to the facility and its many elements during the occupation
 - Owners notes about needed upgrades¹³.
- **COBie** → COBie is the abbreviation for Construction Operations Building Information Exchange) and although it may sound strange and unfamiliar, COBie is a very simple and clear format for delivering building assets data. It is just an XML spreadsheet file with some rules on the structuring and content of the provided data. The COBie spreadsheet contains several tabs which list information on the building's facilities, floors, spaces, systems, installed equipment, documents, etc. Every entry in a worksheet is connected with another one from another worksheet which says "The window XY is in room Z" or "Room Z is on the Nth floor". It is intended to work as a convenient reference on information that is otherwise hidden into the huge amount of drawings and files accompanying a construction project. This makes it a very useful tool for owners, facility managers, and maintenance personnel – people who were not involved in the construction process and aren't interested with every nitty-gritty detail of it but need this data output for their tasks.¹⁴
- **ISO 12006-3:2007** → Building construction — Organization of information about construction works — Part 3: Framework for object-oriented information

¹³ <https://technical.buildingsmart.org/standards/bcf/>

¹⁴ <https://cobuilder.com/en/what-is-cobie-a-simple-outline/>

ISO 12006-3:2007 specifies a language-independent information model which can be used for the development of dictionaries used to store or provide information about construction works. It enables classification systems, information models, object models and process models to be referenced from within a common framework.¹⁵

- **ISO 23386** → Building information modeling and other digital processes used in construction — Methodology to describe, author and maintain properties in interconnected data dictionaries.

This document establishes the rules for defining properties used in construction and a methodology for authoring and maintaining them, for a confident and seamless digital share among stakeholders following a BIM process.

Regarding the definition of properties and groups of properties, this document provides:

- definitions of properties and groups of properties as a list of attributes;
- definitions of all the provided attributes.

Regarding the authoring and maintaining process, this document provides:

- definitions and roles of applicants;
- definitions and roles of experts and the commission of experts;
- definitions of request's attributes;
- definitions of expert's attributes;
- requirements to establish the management rules to interconnect data dictionaries through the mapping process for properties and groups of properties.

To apply the methodology of this document, it is presupposed that the following are in place:

- an established governance model for a data dictionary;
- a framework for a network of data dictionaries.

It is not in the scope of this document to provide the content of the interconnected data dictionaries.¹⁶

- **ISO 23387** → Building information modeling (BIM) — Data templates for construction objects used in the life cycle of built assets — Concepts and principles

This document sets out the principles and structure for data templates for construction objects. It is developed to support digital processes using machine-readable formats using a standard data structure to exchange information about any type of construction object, e.g. product, system, assembly, space, building, etc., used in the inception, brief, design, production, operation, and demolition of facilities.

This document provides the specification of a taxonomy model that defines concepts from ISO 12006-3:2007, i.e. objects, collections, and relationships between them, to support the information need for the specific purpose of the data template.

This document provides an EXPRESS specification with extensions of the EXPRESS-G notation and specification from ISO 12006-3:2007. These extensions have been provided to support market needs developed since the publication of ISO 12006-3 in 2007.

This document provides the rules for linking between data templates and IFC classes within a data dictionary based on ISO 12006-3:2007.

This document provides the rules for linking between data templates and classification systems within a data dictionary based on ISO 12006-3:2007.

¹⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/38706.html>

¹⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/75401.html>

The target audience of this document is software developers and not construction industry domain experts appointed to create data templates based on sources describing information needs.

It is not in the scope of this document to provide the content of any data templates. The data structure provided is intended to be used for developing specific data templates based on standards developed in ISO/IEC, CEN/CENELEC, national standardization organizations, or other sources describing information needs.¹⁷

- **bSDD** → The buildingSMART Data Dictionary (bSDD) is an online service that hosts classifications and their properties, allowed values, units, and translations. The bSDD allows linking between all the content inside the database. It provides a standardized workflow to guarantee data quality and information consistency.

BIM modelers use the bSDD to have easy and efficient access to all kinds of standards to enrich their model. BIM Managers use the bSDD to check BIM data for validity. Advanced users use the contents from the bSDD to check compliance, automatically find manufactured products, extend IFC, create Information Delivery Specifications (IDS), and much more.

Besides national classification systems (Uniclass, Minnd, etc) and application-specific standards (ETIM, UniversalTypes, IfcAirport, etc) project-specific, National and company-specific standards can be stored in bSDD as well. The internal structure can facilitate ISO 12006-3, ISO 23386, and Linked Data publications.¹⁸

- **ISO/DIS 22057** → Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works – Data templates for the use of EPDs for construction products in BIM¹⁹. This standard is under development and will facilitate the choice of products with low environmental impact: The Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) is a document that describes the environmental impact related to the production of a specific product quantity or service: for example energy and raw material consumption, waste generation, atmospheric emissions and discharges into water bodies.
- **IFC4.COD.1** Construction Objects Data View Part 1 The scope of this standard is to define the syntactic characteristics of a generic structure to transport data about construction objects based on EN ISO 16739-1:2018, prEN ISO 23386, and prEN ISO 23387.

The application of this standard allows stakeholders in the construction industry to structure, govern, update, maintain and transport their information about construction objects (e.g. product data) through a machine-interpretable format.

In addition, several stakeholders of the process can make the most out of their software technologies, avoiding data replication as well as saving time and improving both quality and transparency. The scenario within which this standard applies affects producers, designers, constructors, facility, and property managers.

The syntactic approach considers as the primary objective the ability to reuse specifications given in the international standard EN ISO 16739-1:2018. This specific goal is reached by the delivery of the Model View Definition “Construction Objects Data View” (COD) which is made available alongside the others MVD already issued.

¹⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/75403.html>

¹⁸ <https://www.buildingsmart.org/users/services/buildingsmart-data-dictionary/>

¹⁹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/72463.html>

Software houses and software application developers can use this standard to implement interfaces for importing and exporting constructions object according to the official standard EN ISO 16739-1:2018.²⁰

- **Smart contracts** are simply programs stored on a blockchain that run when predetermined conditions are met. They typically are used to automate the execution of an agreement so that all participants can be immediately certain of the outcome, without any intermediary's involvement or time loss. They can also automate a workflow, triggering the next action when conditions are met.

Conclusions

The digitization of the building domain is continuously growing, producing standards that will not only facilitate the exchange of information in a collaborative environment but will also allow new ways of conceiving the buildings. Buildings are “living bodies” and they must be cared for like a human being and, like a human being, the older you get the more you need to be cared for. The standards provide the tools to take care of our buildings along their lifecycle till their “final destination”, that is the decommissioning trying to reduce as much as possible the environmental impact , or the continuous integrated conservation in case of listed historical buildings.

Many standards are already published, others are under development but still very few engineers and architects use them. The reason is both the resistance to the change and the lack of knowledge. The buildingSMART community is an open context where all professionals can increase their competencies and contribute to the definitions of standards that will allow them to work better, faster and contribute to build a zero-energy building stock by 2050.

²⁰ <https://buildingsmart.github.io/ProductData/>